

Comparison of Methods of Estimating Potential Evapotranspiration: A Case Study of Umuagwo Town, Imo State, Nigeria

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Abstract: Due to the growing population of humans, animals, and plants in our environment. There is unhealthy competition for the usage of scarce water resources for efficient crop cultivation. Hence, the need for reliable data on the potential evapotranspiration for agricultural fields. This study was designed to compare potential evapotranspiration estimates from different methods such as Hargreaves, Blaney Morin, Modified Hargreaves and Blaney-Criddle methods with FAO recommended Penman-Monteith method. The results were statistically analyzed using parameters such as Mean Absolute Error (MAE), Mean Square Error (MSE), Root Mean Square Error (RMSE), Correlation of Coefficient (r), and coefficient of determination (r^2). Blaney-Criddle, Hargreaves, Blaney Morin, and Modified Hargreaves yielded MAE of -0.31, 1.12, -1.16, and -1.66, respectively. MSE results showed Blaney-Criddle (0.24), Hargreaves (1.37), Blaney Morin (2.17), and Modified Hargreaves (3.96). FAO-24 Blaney-Criddle, Blaney Morin and Modified Hargreaves methods overestimated the mean daily ETo from the Penman-Monteith method by about 9.17%, 37.17% and 50.77%, respectively. However, FAO-24 Blaney-Criddle method underestimated the mean daily ETo by 34.25%. The cumulative estimated monthly ETo of FAO-24 Blaney-Criddle, Blaney Morin and Modified Hargreaves methods were 1304.16, 1611.92, and 1796.37mm, respectively. These results were 9.50, 35.34, and 50.83% higher than the 1191.02mm obtained from the FAO-recommended Penman-Monteith method. The estimated monthly cumulative ETo for Hargreaves method was 34.21% lower than that obtained from the recommended FAO Penman-Monteith method. Modified Hargreaves method generated the highest average daily ETo (5.96 mm/day) estimates whereas Hargreaves method estimated the lowest average ETo (2.07 mm/day). Amongst all the estimation methods compared with the FAO-recommended Penman-Monteith method, mean ETo estimates from FAO-24 Blaney-Criddle method showed very close agreement. The performance evaluation of the methods compared to the recommended FAO-56 Penman-Monteith method produced a performance ranking of Blaney-Criddle, Hargreaves, Blaney Morin, and Modified Hargreaves methods in decreasing order of accuracy.

Keywords: *Potential Evapotranspiration, estimation methods, Penman-Monteith Method, Umuagwo*

Introduction

Water for agriculture is limited in supply, thereby making its efficient utilization crucial for effective mitigation of water crisis across the globe. Evaporation and transpiration play significant roles in the hydrological cycle. Evapotranspiration (ET) which is the combination of evaporation and transpiration, plays an important role in water management and design in agricultural production (Yingjie *et al*, 2023). According to Anwar *et al*, (2023), ET combines three processes such as soil and vegetation, evaporation, and transpiration. There exist four concepts crucial in understanding the term evapotranspiration, which is as follows: (1) Potential evapotranspiration (PET) is the maximal rate of evaporation with excess soil moisture given a particular climatic condition; (2) Reference evapotranspiration which assumes an excess of soil moisture, is described as the rate of ET from a hypothetical reference crop with a height of 0.12m, a bulk surface resistance of 70 s m^{-1} , and an albedo of 0.23; (3) Crop evapotranspiration can be defined as the water losses from a cropped field under standard (optimal) or nonstandard conditions; (4) Actual evapotranspiration from vegetation/crop refers to the water losses affected by hydrological (e.g., soil moisture)

and meteorological status, as well as vegetation/crop phenology.

In most cases, water losses during crop cultivation occur majorly from evapotranspiration. Thus, it could be said to be crop water requirement is directly proportional to evapotranspiration (Anyanwu *et al.*, 2016). The need for accurate estimation of ET for studies involving simulation of crop yield, design of irrigation systems, hydrological water balance, and water resources planning and management. Studies have focused on the improvement of existing reference ET estimations due to their wide application in crop growth and hydrological studies. Penman-Monteith FAO-56 (PM-56) method is regarded as the most reliable and accurate method for estimating reference ET compared to other existing ET estimation methods (Awari *et al*, 2018). PM-56 is considered the best consisting of major physical parameters governing aerodynamic and energy exchanges affecting ET (Obioma *et al.*, 2015). The method performs better than other methods in the world (Ilesanmi *et al.*, 2014). Estimations using this method require more data compared to other methods. This is a serious challenge because the availability of data is difficult in developing countries of the world. Penman-Monteith FAO-56 (PM-56) requires data such as air temperature, relative

humidity, solar radiation, and wind speed, which pose serious challenges because these climatic parameters are not readily available at different meteorological stations.

According to Anwar, S. A. (2021), depending on the climatic conditions, different empirical methods were developed. These methods were regarded as temperature-based methods, commonly used among them is the Hargreaves- Samani (HS-Base method) which is also recommended by Food Agriculture Organization (FAO) as a possible alternative method for estimating PET in situations where weather data are not available. For better ET estimation, the HS-based method requires empirical coefficients for mean temperature and solar radiation and mean temperature calibrated locally. This method produces a better output in temperate areas. Penman-Monteith FAO-56 (PM-56) method for estimating potential evapotranspiration is approved by FAO and considered the most accurate, reliable, and standardized method.

In a previous study by Egbuikwem and Obiechefu (2017), values for potential evaporation using different estimation

Materials and Method

The study was carried out at the Department of Agricultural and Biosystems Engineering,

methods (FAO 24 Blaney-Criddle, Hargreaves (1975), Modified Hargreaves, Blaney Morin and Piche Atmometer) were determined. Blaney Morin's method generated higher values compared to other methods while Piche Atmometer recorded the lowest mean value.

This study was designed to compare estimated PET from Penman-Monteith FAO-56 (PM-56) to estimations from other methods. This will help in determining PET estimates closest to Penman-Monteith FAO-56 (PM-56). This study became necessary considering the limited supply of climatological data in different regions within developing countries and the complex equations on energy balance required by the Penman-Monteith FAO-56 (PM-56) method. The study is limited to the comparative performance of five different PET estimation methods namely; FAO 24 Blaney-Criddle, Hargreaves (1975), Modified Hargreaves, Blaney Morin, and Penman-Monteith FAO-56 (PM). The outcome of this study will be beneficial to farmers, researchers, scientists, and government agencies (ministries of Environment; Agriculture; and Water Development).

Faculty of Engineering, University of Agriculture and Environmental Sciences, Umuagwo, Imo State, Nigeria. The study area

is situated at 5°33' E and 6°95' N with an elevation of 13.7±8.0 m above sea level. An average monthly meteorological data for the period 2008 to 2018 in respect of maximum and minimum temperature (Tmax/Tmin, °C); maximum and minimum relative humidity (RHmax, RHmin, %); wind speed (WS, ms-1) at the height of 2.0 m and sunshine hours (SSHr, hr) was collected from Anambra Imo River Basin Development Authority accredited weather station. The ETo was estimated using FAO 24 Blaney-Criddle, Hargreaves (1975), Modified Hargreaves, Blaney Morin, and Penman-Monteith FAO-56 (PM). Estimated ETo from these models were used to compare ETo estimated by Penman-Monteith FAO-56 (PM) being a standardized method for estimation of ETo. A brief description of ETo estimation methods is presented as follows;

Blaney-Criddle

According to Doorenbos and Pruitt (1977), the Blaney-Criddle method of estimation of ETo rely on linear relationships between the

Hargreaves Method

This was derived from Alfa fescue grass lysimeter data for a period of eight years from Davis California. Hargreaves and Samani (1975) recommended the estimation of solar

measured ETo and the 'f' factor. The method is presented using the following expression:

$$ETo = a + b f \quad (1).$$

where f is the Blaney-Criddle factor

$$f = P(0.46T_{mean} + 8.13) \quad (2).$$

a and b are coefficients where;

$$a = 0.0043 RH_{min} - (n/N) - 1.41 \quad (3).$$

$$b = a_0 + a_1 RH_{min} + a_2(n/N) + a_3 ud + a_4 RH_{min} (n/N) + a_5 RH_{min} Ud \quad (4).$$

Where a₀, a₁, a₂, a₃, a₄ and a₅ regression coefficients and their values are found as

a₀ = 0.82, a₁ = 0.41 x 10⁻², a₂ = 1.07, a₃ = 0.066, a₄ = -0.60 x 10⁻² and a₅ = -0.60 x 10⁻³, respectively.

T_{mean} is mean daily temperature over the month considered (°C)

P is mean daily percentage of total annual daytime hours

RH_{min} is the average minimum relative humidity of the month (%)

Ud is the average day-time wind speed (km/hr)

N is the maximum sunshine hours (N, hours).

radiation for extraterrestrial radiation using the equation.

$$ETo = 0.000135 RA (TC + 17.8) \quad (5)$$

where TC is the mean monthly minimum temperatures in °C,
 RA is extraterrestrial solar radiation in MJ m⁻² d⁻¹

r_{daily} = daily radiation

r_{max} = maximum monthly radiation,

T = temperature (°C)

R = daily relative humidity (%)

Modified Hargreaves Method

The Hargreaves method was modified taking into consideration minimum and maximum temperature in estimating ETo. Allen et al. (1998), presented the modified method in FAO-56 stating the equation below;

$$E_{To} = 0.0023(T_{\text{max}} - T_{\text{min}})^{0.5} (T_{\text{mean}} + 17.8)Ra \quad (6).$$

where;

ETo is Potential evapotranspiration (mm day⁻¹)

Tmean = daily mean air temperature (°C)

Tmax = daily maximum air temperature (°C)

Tmin = daily minimum air temperature (°C)

Ra = extraterrestrial radiation (mm day⁻¹)

Blaney–Morin Nigeria (BMN)

The evapotranspiration is computed using the formulas developed by Blaney –Morin Nigeria (Duru, 1984). It states;

$$ET = r_f(0.45T+8)(520 - R^{1.31})100 \quad (7).$$

where;

ET = evapotranspiration (mm/day)

r_f = radiation ratio / fraction = $r_{\text{daily}}/r_{\text{max}}$

Penman Monteith Method

The estimated ETo was calculated using the FAO recommended CROPWAT model. The following parameters were provided for the estimation of ETo; location, minimum and maximum temperature, relative humidity, sun hours and wind

Performance of Models

The estimated ETo from different methods were compared using statistical indices with the FAO recommended Penman-Monteith FAO-56 (PM-56) method to attest to their level of reliability and accuracy. The statistical indices are Mean absolute error (MAE), Mean square error (MSE), Coefficient of determination and Standard Deviation (SD).

Mean Absolute Error (MAE)

MAE measures the average absolute deviation of the estimated ETo from other models compare to the recommended Penman-Monteith FAO-56 (PM-56) method. It can be determined by the equation below;

$$\text{MAE} = (1/n) \sum_{i=1}^n (O_i - P_i) \quad (8).$$

where;

n is total number of observations

O_i is actual value of PM-56

P_i is the compared model variable.

Mean Square Error (MSE)

MSE measures the difference between an estimated ETo from other models compare to the true value from recommended Penman-Monteith FAO-56 (PM-56) method. MSE determines the average of the square of the 'error'. The MSE is determined by using following formula:

$$\text{MSE} = (1/n) \sum_{i=1}^n (O_i - P_i)^2 \quad (9).$$

Root Mean Square Error (RMSE)

(11).

Coefficient of Determination (r²)

r² gives information on the goodness of fit of used model. It measures how well the regression line approximates or correlates with the real data points. r² of 1.0 implies that the data fits the regression line. r² is determined by using the formula below:

$$r^2 = \frac{\left(\sum_{i=1}^n (P_i - \bar{P})(P_i - \bar{O}) \right)^2}{\sum_{i=1}^n (P_i - \bar{P})^2 (O_i - \bar{O})^2} \quad (12).$$

RMSE measures the differences between an estimated ETo from other models compare to the true value from recommended Penman-Monteith FAO-56 (PM-56) method. RMSE can be relied upon because of its accuracy. The individual differences are known as residuals. RMSE aggregates the differences as a single measure of predictive power. This can be calculated using the equation below:

$$\text{RMSE} = \sqrt{(1/n) \sum_{i=1}^n (O_i - P_i)^2} \quad (10).$$

Coefficient of Correlation (r)

The value of r can be determined by the formula below. The values of r lie between -1 to +1. When r = +1, it denotes perfect positive correlation between the variables. When r = -1, it denotes perfect negative correlation between the variables. When r = 0, means no existing relationship between variables.

$$r = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (P_i - \bar{P})(P_i - \bar{O})}{\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n (P_i - \bar{P})^2 (O_i - \bar{O})^2}}$$

Results and Discussion

Results

The daily and monthly cumulative estimated potential evapotranspiration was calculated using different ETo estimation Models for Umuagwo, Imo State. These estimation models are namely; Penman Monteith FAO-56, FAO-24 Blaney-Criddle, Hargreaves, Blaney Morin, and Modified Hargreaves methods. Estimated daily ETo values were obtained using weekly mean estimates throughout the study as presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Estimated daily and monthly cumulative ETo estimation methods

Month	Penman Monteith FAO-56 mm/day	Penman Monteith FAO-56 Monthly ETo mm/month	FAO-24 Blaney-Criddle mm/day	FAO-24 Blaney-Criddle Monthly ETo mm/month	Hargreaves mm/day	Hargreaves Monthly ETo mm/month	Blaney Morin mm/day	Blaney Morin Monthly ETo mm/month	Modified Hargreaves mm/day	Modified Hargreaves Monthly ETo mm/month
January	3.12	96.72	3.62	112.22	2.17	67.27	5.68	176.08	5.54	171.74
February	3.48	194.16	3.72	216.38	2.24	129.99	5.37	326.44	5.96	338.62
March	3.67	307.93	3.68	330.46	2.21	198.50	4.75	473.69	5.76	517.18
April	3.65	417.43	3.65	439.96	2.19	264.20	4.56	610.49	5.49	681.88
May	3.73	533.06	3.59	551.25	2.15	330.85	4.34	745.03	5.52	853.00
June	3.07	625.16	3.52	656.85	2.12	394.45	3.84	860.23	4.13	976.90
July	2.78	711.34	3.44	763.49	2.07	458.62	3.40	965.63	3.37	1081.37
August	2.85	799.69	3.45	870.44	2.07	522.79	3.43	1071.96	3.54	1191.11
September	2.91	886.99	3.49	975.14	2.10	585.79	3.70	1182.96	3.85	1306.61
October	3.10	983.09	3.52	1084.26	2.12	651.51	4.00	1306.96	4.44	1444.25
November	3.49	1087.79	3.61	1192.56	2.17	716.61	4.73	1448.86	5.62	1612.85
December	3.33	1191.02	3.60	1304.16	2.16	783.57	5.26	1611.92	5.92	1796.37
Average	3.27		3.57		2.15		4.42		4.93	

Estimated daily and monthly cumulative ETo values computed in Table 1 using relevant formulae designated equations 1 to 7. Summary of results obtained are presented in Figures 1 to 8.

Fig 1: Comparing average daily ETo using Penman Monteith and Blaney Criddle methods

Fig 2: Comparing average daily ETo using Penman Monteith and Hargreaves methods

Fig 3: Comparing average daily ETo using Penman Monteith and Blaney Morin methods

Fig 4: Comparing average daily E_{to} using Penman Monteith and Modified Hargreaves methods

Fig 5: Comparing average cumulative E_{to} using Penman Monteith and Blaney Criddle methods

Fig 6: Comparing average cumulative E_{to} using Penman Monteith and Hargreaves methods

Fig 7: Comparing average cumulative ETo using Penman Monteith and Blaney Morin methods

Fig 8: Comparing average cumulative ETo using Penman Monteith and Modified Hargreaves methods

Estimated average daily ETo values computed in Table 1 using relevant formulae designated equations 1 to 7 were statistically analyzed and presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Statistical Comparison of ETo estimation methods with Penman Monteith FAO 56

	MAE	MSE	RMSE	r	r ²
Blaney Criddle	-0.31	0.24	0.49	-0.01	0.0001
Hargreaves	1.12	1.37	1.17	0.19	0.0361
Blaney Morin	-1.16	2.17	1.47	-0.14	0.0196
Modified Hargreaves	-1.66	3.96	1.99	-0.15	0.0225

Discussion

The average estimated daily ETo using different methods was compared with the FAO standard recommended ETo estimation method (FAO-56 Penman-Monteith). Data presented in Table 1 show that Blaney Morin and Modified Hargreaves methods overestimated ETo whereas the Hargreaves method underestimated ETo when compared with ETo estimates of FAO-56 Penman-Monteith. FAO-24 Blaney-Criddle method estimated values that were relatively close to values from FAO-56 Penman-Monteith. The modified Hargreaves method gave the highest average daily ETo (5.96 mm/day) estimates whereas the Hargreaves method estimated the lowest average ETo (2.07 mm/day). ETo estimations from Blaney Morin and Modified Hargreaves methods showed a high level of variation as compared to ETo estimates of FAO-56 Penman-Monteith.

The estimated mean daily ETo of Umuagwo, Imo State, Nigeria obtained from different estimation methods were statistically analyzed

to ascertain their comparative performance with the FAO recommended Penman-Monteith method using statistical indices such as; Mean Absolute Error (MAE), Mean Square Error (MSE), Root Mean Square Error (RMSE), Correlation of Coefficient (r) and coefficient of determination (r^2) as shown in Table 2. The data obtained show that amongst the five ETo estimation methods, the FAO-24 Blaney-Criddle method performed better than other estimation methods with the lowest MAE, MSE, RMSE, and r. The modified Hargreaves method had the highest MAE, MSE, RMSE, and r (Table 2).

Table 1 shows the comparison of the daily and cumulative monthly estimated ETo from various methods to FAO recommended Penman-Monteith method. Data show that FAO-24 Blaney-Criddle, Blaney Morin and Modified Hargreaves methods overestimated the mean daily ETo from the Penman-Monteith method by about 9.17%, 37.17%, and 50.77%, respectively. However, the FAO-24 Blaney-Criddle method underestimated the

mean daily ETo by 34.25%. The cumulative estimated monthly ETo of FAO-24 Blaney-Criddle, Blaney Morin, and Modified Hargreaves methods were 1304.16, 1611.92, and 1796.37mm, respectively. These results were 9.50, 35.34, and 50.83% higher than the 1191.02mm obtained from the FAO-recommended Penman-Monteith method. The estimated monthly cumulative ETo for the Hargreaves method was 34.21% lower than that obtained from the recommended FAO Penman-Monteith method.

Amongst all the estimation methods compared with the FAO-recommended Penman-Monteith method, mean ETo estimates from the FAO-24 Blaney-Criddle method showed the closest agreement based on statistical analysis results obtained from this study (Table 2). However, other methods used in estimating ETo ranked in decreasing

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References

Allen, R. G., Pereira, L. S., Raes, D. and Smith, M. (1998). Crop Evapotranspiration. Guidelines for

order as follows; Hargreaves, Blaney Morin, and Modified Hargreaves methods.

Conclusion

Potential evapotranspiration estimates of Umuagwo town which is located in Imo state, Nigeria were studied using different estimation methods. The daily and cumulative monthly potential evapotranspiration (ETo) of the study area was determined using various methods namely; Penman Monteith FAO-56, FAO-24 Blaney-Criddle, Hargreaves, Blaney Morin and Modified Hargreaves methods. The performance evaluation of the methods compared to the recommended FAO-56 Penman-Monteith method produced a performance ranking of Blaney-Criddle, Hargreaves, Blaney Morin, and Modified Hargreaves methods in decreasing order of accuracy.

Computing Crop Water Requirements. FAO Irrigation and Drainage, Paper No. 56, FAO, Rome.

Anyanwu, V. K., Okereke, N. A. A., Egwuonwu, C. C. and Oguoma, O. N. (2016). Reliability Studies of Six Evapotranspiration Models for Owerri in South Eastern Nigeria. *International Journal of Agriculture and Biosciences*, 5(4), 147-150.

Anwar, S. A. (2021). On the contribution of dynamic leaf area index in simulating the African climate using a regional

- climate model (RegCM4). *Theor Appl Climatol*, 143,119–129. doi.org/10.1007/s00704-020-03414-x
- Anwar, S. A., Malcheva, K. and Srivastava, A. (2023). Estimating the potential evapotranspiration of Bulgaria using a high-resolution regional climate model. *Theoretical and Applied Climatology*. 152:1175–1188. doi.org/10.1007/s00704-023-04438-9
- Awari, H. W., Khodke U. M. and Ingle, V. K. (2018). Comparative Performance Of Different Reference Evapotranspiration Estimation Methods For Parbhani. *Trends In Biosciences*, 11(4), 1-5.
- Doorenbos, J. and Pruitt, W. O. (1977). Guidelines for predicting crop water requirements. Irrigation and Drainage Paper 24 (revised) Food and Agricultural Organization of the United Nations, Rome.
- Duru, J. O. (1984). Blaney –Morin – Nigeria. Evapotranspiration Models. *Journal of Hydrology*, 70:71 – 83.
- Egbuikwem P. N. and Obiechefu G. C. (2017). Evaluation of Evapotranspiration Models for Waterleaf crop using Data from Lysimeter. ASABE Annual International Meeting, Spokane, Washington, USA.
- Hargreaves, G. H. and Samani, Z. A. (1985). Reference Crop Evapotranspiration from Temperature. *Appl. Eng. Agric*, 1(2), 96–99.
- Ilesanmi, O. A., Oguntunde, P. G., Olufayo, A. A. (2014). Evaluation of Four ETo Models for IITA Stations in Ibadan, Onne and Kano, Nigeria. *Journal of Environment and Earth Science*, 4(5), 89-97.
- Obioma, C. P., Nwaigwe, K. N. and Okereke, C. D. (2015). Development and Evaluation of a Weighable Lysimeter to Determine Crop Evapotranspiration. *International Journal of Research in Engineering and Technology*, 4(3), 2319-1163|
- Yingjie, L., Tao, L., Hui, H. and Xuemei Z. (2023). Short-term prediction of reference crop evapotranspiration based on machine learning with different decomposition methods in arid areas of China. *Agricultural Water Management*, Pg:1-17. doi.org/10.1016/j.agwat.2023.108175